

The Holistic Development of Society The Contributions of the Christian Church

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ABSTRACT: This paper aims to reflect upon the role of the Christian Church as a natural factor in the holistic development of society. In this respect, the main role of the Church will be viewed in light of the twenty–first century Christianity, in the context of the global society. Factors such as access to information, the increase of knowledge, and the emergence of knowledge–based society in a globalizing world often give the impression that they are the main development drivers of the postmodern society. However, the development of society is naturally linked to the development of the individual within different contexts such as provided by family, school, church and society. From a Christian perspective the holistic transformation of humanity and the restoration of universal order is the ultimate goal of the divine in the “relocation” of His Kingdom on earth. During the twentieth century, the trend manifested by the Church was more on the edge of social responsibility as an agent of a secular society, affecting the application of the principle of *Christian responsibility*. According to the principle of Christian responsibility, the relationships within a society are an expression that flows naturally from the relationship with God. Sociologic and religious research combines theological thinking of Christianity with social conditioning, thus giving the Christian Church the responsibility of being a serious contender and agent for a holistic transformation of humanity and of restoring the universal order; thus fulfilling the divine plan.

KEY WORDS: theology, church development, Christian church, holistic society

In the course of human history, whenever humanity is situated at a crossroads it turned its attention to the great events of the past for help at that time and for the future. A careful review of the works on the emergence and history of Christianity can provide enlightenment for the present and inspiration for the future in the context of contemporary society. As Paul the Apostle points out in his letter to the Romans 15:4: „whatever things were written before were written for our learning, that we through patience and comfort of the scriptures might have hope.”¹

The study of the history of Christianity is invaluable for researchers and for the layman, for personal development and therefore of human society. In this sense historian Earle E. Cairns says “by exposing the genetic development of Christianity, the New Testament Church history is what the New Testament is to the Old Testament.”² Given this perspective, after a brief definition of the terms we will describe and we will see how early Christianity helped the holistic development of the society back then and after that we will see the contribution of Christianity in today's society.

Finally we will present findings on the observations and findings on the contribution of Christianity to the holistic development of human society.

For a brief definition of the terms, I use *Dicționarul Explicativ al Limbii Române* also known as DEX:

HOLÍSM: Concept underlying the irreducibility of the sum of the parts, meaning that some of its features can not be explained in terms of properties and relationships of its components. - From fr. holisme.³

CHRISTIANITY: All forms of faith in the person and writings that contain the words and teachings of Jesus Christ. - Christian + suf. -ism (After fr. Christianisme).⁴

Early Christian Contributions to the Development of a Holistic Society

Christianity is born from Judaism not only as “an extension of Judaism,”⁵ but as a prophetic fulfillment in the life, ministry, death

and resurrection of Jesus Christ, shortly after his ascension to the Father, during Pentecost (Acts 2:1–4), when the Holy Spirit came upon a group of faithful Hebrew.

This group has grown quickly through the influence of the Holy Spirit (Acts 2:47), especially after the martyrdom of Stephen (Acts 8:1), shortly transforming into a religious movement that developed quickly with an outstanding spread in the context of the then.

Christianity appears as a reform movement of Judaism, at first the proclamation of the Gospel took place in synagogues and the rapid growth led to Christians holding their meetings in mostly private homes. However the Christian Church was a distinct group, separated from synagogue life.

Christianity originally was addressed to Jews, after the conversion of centurion Cornelius (Acts 10) at the Council of Jerusalem in the year A.D.49 it was decided that the new religion should also address the Gentiles, thus Christianity became a religion distinct from Judaism.

The essence of early Christianity was Judaism which proclaimed monotheism, the highest ethics based on the 10 commandments, a philosophy of the emerging history and the messianic hope all based on a book Torah, later called the Old Testament.

Greek contribution to Christianity's emergence and development was preparing the context by creating a vacuum through the failure of the Greek philosophy and then through the Greek language that was used throughout the Roman Empire, through which Christianity's message was forwarded.

The Romans contribution to the development of Christianity was materialized through Roman conquests that led to blurring the beliefs of the conquered nations creating a common ethos, also the Roman Empire built an infrastructure of communication roads, which helped to spread Christianity in a relatively short time.

Thus Christianity fueled from the spiritual sources of Judaism, expressed by means of Greek culture and favored by the infrastructures and context of the Roman Empire, could become the only universal religion with a global historical impact.

The Central doctrine of the Christian message is Jesus Christ called by prophets and disciples Messiah, born in Palestine in year 5 BC, and died crucified in year A.D.30.

Jesus Christ did not dispute the Jewish religion, but realized fulfillment of the prophecies concerning Him, and exceeding the limits placed by the Jews establishing a universal religion based on love of God and love of neighbor as a fulfillment of the moral law, promising all eternal life in the Kingdom of God.

Christianity based on the teachings promoted by the Apostles was centered around the life, death, resurrection, and teachings of Jesus Christ, Son of God, who gave Himself as a sacrifice for the redemption of sinners, became the Savior and Lord of those who believe in Him, had a simple way of worship.

Christians gathered in homes or in places safe from persecutors and who ran the meeting was preaching from the teaching of Jesus Christ and the apostles then they prayed together, sang Christian hymns and the Lord's Supper was celebrated at the end of the meeting.

Georges Florovsky, a professor of church history, captures the moment of Christianity's emergence by saying that "it entered the historical scene as a Society or Community, as a new social order or even as a new social dimension, as a Church."⁶

The Church is the divine-human institution that arose through divine presence manifested in the lives of believers at Pentecost. Best understood word for church is the assembly, as historian Adrien Ladrière says "when the Apostle Paul writes to the Church or Assembly of God which is at Corinth, he goes to all the Christians of Corinth. But when he says, 'Christ loved the Assembly' it means all true believers, washed of their sins in the precious blood of Christ, but being still on earth. (1 Cor. 1:2; Acts 20:28; Calendula 2; Eph. 1:22, 5:25)⁷

Because the Church is made up of those born of God (John 3:9) and are united with each other and with the Lord Jesus all having a new life, is called the body of Jesus, he is the Head (Eph 1:22-23; Col. 1:18; Rom.12:4-5). Each believer is thus a member of this body being in close connection with each other and with the Head Jesus Christ.

Thus the Church becomes the incarnation of the divine through the Holy Spirit to those who have accepted Jesus Christ as Lord in their lives, revealing His character in their lives.

Church members are endowed and equipped for service to others in the Church and society through gifts of the Holy Spirit (1 Cor. 12:1–13).

The divine purpose for the church is to be “a spectacle to angels and men” to be ‘light of the world’ and ‘salt of the earth’ (Mat 5:13–14) and ‘to give His people knowledge of salvation, which is the forgiveness of sins; because of the great mercy of our God, after which we looked at the Sun rising from on high to give light to them that sit in darkness and in the shadow of death, to guide our feet into the way of peace.” (Luke 1:77–79)

Church’s role in society is “to ready for the Lord a people well prepared for Him” (Luke 1:17) for His second coming.

To accomplish this work the Church is involved in society in existential areas such as social, health, education and spiritual.

The social fund of early Christianity was investigated by one of the most experienced specialists in the field theologian Gerd Theissen, who published an extensive study dedicated to social history.

Gerd Theissen defines four trends available in early Christianity. First is about urbanization. Even if Christianity started with people in rural areas it was spread to the cities, where due to the different relationship between Jews and pagans led to conflicts with local and imperial powers.

Second, is the tendency of universalizing openness to all sympathizers removing the command of circumcision—which also led to conflicts.

A third trend is the dynamic of the growth of social advancement. Early Christianity was born in the lower social strata, but according to Plinius⁸ in the second century there were Christians in all walks of life. And this has led Corinth to tension between rich and poor, between the powerful and the weak.⁹

Lastly Theissen talks about the trend of spiritualization because Jesus promised freedom from sin for all people. Early Christianity promised freedom to all, especially the inner worth—which also

created conflicts. Just as the local aristocracy was united and formed the upper class of society, early Christianity formed in the lower stratum of society a concurrent movement that has spread quickly and was open to all social classes.¹⁰

Theissen emphasizes in early Christianity both the transfer of values from the top to bottom class of society, which led to the “democratization” of aristocratic values. For example, the aid of others or generosity towards enemies were features and privileges only of those in power.

Goodness saying “is more blessed to give than to receive”—also constituted a feature, an aristocratic rule. So the poor widow who donated all her pennies becomes an example of noble generosity. Even the golden rule—valid for the privileged classes in ancient times, was proclaimed in Mat 7:12; Luke 6:31 for all people, thus repeatedly a ruler, aristocrat behaviour is transferred to all.¹¹

Notice how Theissen demonstrates that the early church was able to provide models of Roman society which had been in operation for all members of society, starting from a personal relationship with Jesus, then benefiting from belonging to a universal community within which an inclusive extraterritorial culture is developing, revealing the full potential of early Christianity.

Early Christianity penetrated the ancient society with Christian ideas and changed people’s concept about the world and life, thus entering into competition with other schools of thought. One of the primary aspects of early community life that highlights this change is the charitable activity “and sold their land and goods and distributed them to all, as any had needed each” (Acts 2:45).

That Joseph, also called Barnabas by the apostles meaning Son of Encouragement a Levite from Cyprus (Acts 4:36), sold his land inherited from his parents and “brought the money and laid it at the apostles’ feet”, reveals the organization of the early Christian community, coordinated at first by the apostles and entrusted to the seven deacons when the number of Christians increased. (Acts 6:1–6)

Another important aspect described in Acts 6 is a clear distinction between the apostles involvement in the spiritual—educational sphere and the social sphere which is supported by deacons. Also it is seen in the social sphere the care for the poor

categories widows, orphans, the poor and the foreigners, social protection measures covered in Judaism. We note that since the beginning early Christianity adopted a positive attitude about material things. In the Christian belief God is the Sovereign Creator and Lord of all things. The man is the manager of all goods received from his Creator.

All material things are made available to the man as gifts because using them on his journey on earth he can live decently and managing them after the Christian principles, the character of man to be knighted and ready to enter the Kingdom of God (Matthew 6.33).

The early Christians had a strong sense of identity and belonging. They thought they were a “holy people,” “a holy nation,” a “chosen people,” a new society that fulfills God’s plan, as the Apostle Peter taught. (1 Peter 2:9.)

Thus, the early Christians had a sense of extra-territorial (Phil. 3:20) outside the existing social order; they were “travelers” or “foreigners”, but they remained in the society (in the world) fulfilling all the daily duties responsibly, putting divine authority over the human one, being spiritually detached.

Writing about this, the historian Florovsky emphasizes that “this detachment from “the world” can only be temporary, since Christianity by its very nature was a missionary religion and aiming for a universal conversion. The subtle distinction “in the world but not of the world” could not solve this primary problem, since “the world” had to be redeemed and could not be tolerated in its unreformed state.”¹²

In terms of culture Christians have accepted the challenge of meeting the two cultures, Greek and Roman; but they felt called to promote a culture based on new principles, a new perspective, as citizens of a “new country” which is centered on the heavenly Jerusalem.

By the coming, particularly life and resurrection, ascension and placing of Jesus Christ at the right hand of God, ancient culture has received a new dimension which caused major cultural changes in the life of humanity after 33 AD Through contact with other cultures Christianity changed their meaning, giving them the dimension of repentance; the immediate effect was noted as the re-culturalization

of antiquity. The history's ascertainment regarding the Christians - culture relationship, expressed by historian Florovsky reveals that they are not "doomed to the denial of culture", but Christians "must be critical of any cultural situation and measure everything by the measure of Christ."¹³

It is well known that in the New Testament the word "church", "ekklesia", has two different meanings. One meaning is one universal Church, a community of all believers united "in Christ." Another meaning is given by use of the word in the plural, meaning local Christian communities from all places.

Christianity although having a social doctrine and orientation, was above all a community aimed at praising God and rebuild human society on new principles, after the model offered by Him.

The early church besides its social and education preoccupations, was concerned with changing hearts and minds, thus paving the way for ethical and social changes, becoming a model for a new humanity.

The fact that in early Christianity reporting to the divine had a primordial place, made it omnipresent in all humanity's existential aspects.

XXI Century Christianity

Christian vocation to bring the light of truth to every nation, every people and every man (Matt. 28:19), determines and empowers every Christian to openness towards people of other faiths.

In the XIX and XX centuries the world continued to move towards a positivism determined by science and technology, through the process of industrialization, development of means of communication, resource exploitation and economic development.

As recorded by the Orthodox priest and university professor, Ioan Rămureanu, during the last centuries, mankind became increasingly alienated from the Church "especially after the positivism of Auguste Comte seemed to give a form to human development on the way to the "religion of the future" which no longer admits anything except what the positive science admits."¹⁴

The secularization process was the result of a confrontation between the Church and Western culture. The Church tried to sacralize and to expand its authority over the world and as a reaction Western culture gave birth to the process of secularization.

In the next step the process of secularization has caused a shift of the center of gravity of life and culture from God to man, meaning it passed from teocentrism to anthropocentrism. Christianity is abandoned; the man gives up the divine ruling adoring his own reason thus preparing the era of reason.

World secularization has stimulated the development of world science and technology and paved the way for mankind's spiritual regression.

One of the challenges of Christianity in the XXI century is to become ecumenical and catholic again, through openness to the values of contemporary humanity and to support efforts to achieve them.

Advocating for the right to personal freedom Mochael Novak said: "We are, I believe, at the threshold of a new social evolution. Many of the old ways no longer work. We must rethink our goals. We must rethink our methods."¹⁵

Renaissance developed the thinking that led to a scientific rationality, purely functional, experimentally demonstrated which proved bankrupt because it has created an imbalance between technical and moral.

In everyday life, the Christian family, spirituality, personal and social ethics, now plays a vital role for the Church's activity in society. From the sociological perspective, the Church is called to intercede in prayer for those in need, the helpless, underprivileged and powerless.

Churches by the human component of their members, through creation and ontological union of Christ are related to human society. Thus it is called in the postmodern world to promote peace, combat poverty, and work for social protection, health and religious freedom, to teach and to proclaim the Gospel.

Church's task is not only to work to protect the identity and unity but to prepare for the future as a community concerned to transmit Christian values to new generations. It is important for

Christians today to conduct a historical review and update what their ancestors and parents thought and created.

The church of the XXI century is called amidst the global problems of mankind to make visible the divine presence through ordination, intercession and its service in the world.

Citing the Torah in the book of Isaiah, Jesus Christ stated the mission statement of the Church: "The Spirit of the Lord is upon me, because He hath anointed Me to preach the gospel to the poor; sent Me to bind up the brokenhearted, to preach deliverance to the slaves of war and the blind sight; to absolve the weary and to proclaim the grace year of the Lord." (Luke 4:18).

The reign of God means the full transformation of humanity and recreating the world by releasing people from all forms of slavery and oppression, personal and social.

Christianity affirms the value of the transcendent element, the reality of this world is only a pale imitation of the model of eternity, and history records the intention of Christianity to shape society in the image of God's Kingdom.

Conclusions

The emergence of Christianity in the flow of history was like a mighty river flowing over the sides with divine blessings changing its course to refresh the entire humanity. After twenty centuries we can see how Christianity has influenced society, but society has also influenced Christianity.

The rapid spread of early Christianity is one of the most amazing phenomena in the history of mankind.

Of particular interest in researching the social functions of early Christianity have to be primarily taking into account the impact of the new religion.

Christianity brings a qualitative leap from the relational anthropology ideal to the Christological one of the Eucharistic community. Christian behavior derives from this relational reality vertically and horizontally, which constitute the ecclesial community, giving it an interior and exterior dynamic, in solidarity and mission.

Faith, love and hope were the mysteries of the Christian Church, fundamental elements on which was later built what we now call “Western culture.”

History has shown that in many cases, economic considerations have played an important role both in society and in the Church’s life.

Church service is very important, but we must not separate the social and philanthropic work from the spiritual one as the charitable work of the Church is sacramental and pastoral and the social one is the concrete expression, of the former.

The economic crisis, accompanied by a moral crisis, deepens the consequences of the deeply secularized life of today’s society. Man lives only for himself; he lives in an absurd rhetoric that characterizes life.

Today when society is increasingly fragmented and suffers diverse mutations, what can the Church do to help the holistic development of the postmodern society?

History shows that Christianity demonstrated over time a capacity for innovation and potential of adaptation matching the needs of the current time.

Christian Church today also benefits from the potential required for the challenges and needs of contemporary society to adapt its working methods and those of approach to society and peers.

Renewing human society has been and will always be possible through Jesus Christ from the inside out and from individual to society through the cleaning of the spring.

Therefore obtaining a simple life full of love and devotion to Christ, willingness to serve unconditionally and selflessly, the joy to confess Him whatever the cost, the availability to be all things to all, marked the life of Christians in each historical epoch. There were, there are and there will be voices that continue to stand up to preach faith, truth, love, justice, hope that God has been and will be with His creatures. The whole history shows us that nothing lasts without the presence and blessing of God which is in charge of the universe.

NOTES

- ¹ Dumitru Cornilescu, *Biblia*, București: Casa Bibliei, 2010.
- ² Earle E. Cairns, *Creștinismul de-a lungul secolelor* (București: Societatea Misionară Română, 1992), 17.
- ³ Dex-Online 2009. <https://dexonline.ro/> (Last accessed October 19, 2016)
- ⁴ Ibid.
- ⁵ Jonathan Hill, *Istoria Gândirii Creștine* (Oradea: Casa Cărții, 2007), 13.
- ⁶ Georges Florovski, *Creștinism și Cultură* (Belmont, MA: Nordland, 1974), 19.
- ⁷ Adrien Ladrierre, *Biserica sau Adunarea* (Dillenburg: Gute Botschaft Verlag, 1993), 6.
- ⁸ Plin. Ep. XI, 96,9.
- ⁹ Theißen, Gerd, Von Jesus zur urchristlichen Zeichenwelt. „Neutestamentliche Grenzgänge“ im Dialog. (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht GmbH, 2011), 28.
- ¹⁰ Theißen Gerd, Von Jesus zur urchristlichen Zeichenwelt. „Neutestamentliche Grenzgänge“ im Dialog. (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht GmbH, 2011), 29.
- ¹¹ Ibid. 44–45.
- ¹² Florovski, Ibid.
- ¹³ Ibid, 21.
- ¹⁴ Ioan Rămureanu, Milan Șesan, Teodor Bodogae, *Istoria Bisericească Universală, vol. II* (București: Editura Institutului Biblic și de Misiune Al Bisericii Ortodoxe Române, 1993), 337.
- ¹⁵ Michael Novak's ideas had been published as a chapter in Ioan I. Ică, Jr and Germano Marani, eds. *Gândirea Socială a Bisericii* (Sibiu: Deisis, 2002), 418.